

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A COMPARISON OF SENSITIVITY AND SPECIFICITY OF TRANSIENT ELASTOGRAPHY I.E. FIBRO SCAN WITH SERUM AMINOTRANSFERASE LEVELS I.E. ALT & AST IN CHRONIC HCV INFECTED PATIENTS, A RETRO PROSPECTIVE CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY AT LAHORE GENERAL HOSPITAL, LAHORE, PAKISTAN

Syed Muhammad Aqib¹, Bukhtawar Munir², Sifwa Safdar³, Azhar Hussain⁴,
Dr. Junaid Mushtaq⁵

¹⁻²⁴th Year MBBS, Ameer ud Din Medical College Lahore, ³⁴th Year MBBS, Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore, ⁵MBBS, FCPS Gastroenterology, Medicine unit.

Article Received: May 2019

Accepted: June 2019

Published: July 2019

Abstract:

Objective: To assess the validity of Serum Aminotransferase Levels i.e. ALT & AST as fibrosis biomarker, we compared their serum levels with fibro scan for the fibrosis staging and predicting its progression in Pakistani population.

Methods: The retrospective cross sectional study was conducted in medicine unit 1&2 and hepatitis clinic of Lahore General Hospital, Lahore starting from February 15, 2018 to January 11, 2019. We studied 1181 HCV infected patients which were got CBC, LFTs, ELISA, PCR and fibro scan done to perfectly diagnose ongoing hepatitis C infection. In order to differentiate HCV fibrosis progression, we compared the effectiveness of readily available serum aminotransferase Levels i.e. ALT & AST with fibro scan.

Results: An AST had sensitivity of 82.6 and specificity of 79.0 for F4 stage. with AUC=0.883. An ALT for F4 stage, the sensitivity was 57.3, specificity 50.0 with AUC=0.771.

Conclusion: An AST and ALT can predict advance stage of fibrosis and cirrhosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C infection. In these patients, a liver biopsy and fibro scan may not be necessary.

Keywords: Hepatitis C, Blood Platelets, Fibro scan score.

Corresponding author:**Azhar Hussain,**(3rd year MBBS, Ameer Ud Din Medical College, Lahore),Email address: azharhussain0139@gmail.com,

Cell Number: +923037156931

QR code

Please cite this article in press Azhar Hussain et al., A Comparison of Sensitivity and Specificity of Transient Elastography I.E. Fibro scan with serum aminotransferase levels i.e. Alt & ast in chronic hcv infected patients, a retro prospective cross-sectional study at lahore general hospital, lahore, pakistan., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Have you heard the term “Serial Killer”? Yes! Right? Then you will be amazed to know that hepatitis C is “Silent Serial Killer”. Death from hep C is due to liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. According to the report of 2015, 167000 deaths occurred from liver cancer while 326000 from cirrhosis in hepatitis C patients. More than 700000 people die from hepatitis C related diseases every year.

HCV can cause both acute and chronic hepatitis. It is spread from blood to blood contact involving intravenous drug users, blood transfusions, needles stick injuries or vertical transmission. Its envelope proteins often vary their antigenic structure and our immune system can't keep up rendering the vaccine obsolete immediately. Hep C causes inflammation of liver which leads to jaundice, right upper quadrant pain and hepatomegaly. 60-80% become chronic. Lymphocytes infiltrate the portal tract and with chronic inflammation and infection, hepatocytes die. Liver cells and parenchyma are irritated and liver quickly needs to replace them. Some come to fibrosis and cirrhosis or alternatively hepatocytes go into frenzy and reproducing cells become malignant leading to hepatocellular carcinoma. Hep C infection leads to development of cryoglobulins or serum proteins containing IgM that precipitate and cool our temperature.

Globally 71 million people are estimated to be chronically infected. A significant number of those will develop cirrhosis or hepatocellular carcinoma. Pakistan has the world's second highest prevalence of the hepatitis C, second only to Egypt. (WHO, n.d.). HCV is “Silent Serial Killer” because the infected person remains symptomless unless a great amount of damage has occurred. According to a research conducted by U.S Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), 51% of persons living with hepatitis C infection do not know they have the virus. Especially in Pakistan, more than 60% of the population lives in rural areas. They do not have access to quality health facilities. Another huge problem is lack of awareness to get themselves screened for such infections periodically. Also, they are not financially that strong to afford tests like

PCR, ELISA and Fibroscan.

As DAAs have made it possible to achieve 95% cure rate. So the major hurdle today in our way to achieve HCV free world is the timely diagnosis of the infection. This research was carried out to assess how effective are AST and ALT in predicting different stages of fibrosis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The retrospective cross sectional study was conducted in medicine unit 1&2 and hepatitis clinic of Lahore General Hospital, Lahore starting from February 15, 2018 to January 11, 2019. We studied 1181 HCV infected patients which were got CBC, LFTs, ELISA, PCR and fibro scan done to perfectly diagnose ongoing hepatitis C infection. In order to differentiate HCV fibrosis progression, we compared the effectiveness of readily available serum aminotransferase Levels i.e. ALT & AST with fibro scan

Statistical analysis:

SPSS windows version 22 was used to analyze the data. p value of less than 0.05 was considered statically significant. To signify the marked association between stages of liver fibrosis and continuous variables, Spearman's rank correlation was used. We used student t-test to relate arithmetic means and parameters. Various univariate analysis was performed for multiple biomarkers. Receiver Operating Curves (ROC) and AUROC were performed to infer the diagnostic precision of the serum fibrosis indexes along with their cutoff points, sensitivities and specificities.

RESULTS:**Patients Data:**

In this study we included 1181 patients. There are 690(58.4%) female patients and 491(41.6%) are male as shown in table.1. Among them 1092(92.7%) patients are married while 83(7.2%) are unmarried. Occupation related division shows that 414 patients are the housewives, 727 are the laborers and 40 are the working ladies.

Table 1: Showing gender distribution of 1181 patients.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	690	58.4	58.4	58.4
Male	491	41.6	41.6	100.0
Total	1181	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Depicts marital status of patients.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Married	1095	92.7	92.7	92.5
Unmarried	86	7.2	7.2	99.5
Total	1181	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Occupation of the patients.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Housewife	414	35.1	35.1	35.1
Laborer	727	61.6	61.6	96.6
Working Lady	40	3.4	3.4	100.0
Total	1181	100.0	100.0	

Genotype distribution shows that 726(61.5%) patients are 3a, 378(32%) are 1b and 77(6.5%) are 1A.

Table 4: Genotype of the patients.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 3a	726	61.5	61.5	61.5
1b	378	32.0	32.0	93.5
1A	77	6.5	6.5	100.0
Total	1181	100.0	100.0	

Fibrosis stage findings among HCV infected patients shows that among 1181 patients, 581(49.2%) patients are in fibrosis stage F0-F1 stage, 71(6%) patients are in F2 stage, 161(13.6%) patients in F3 and 368(31.2%) patients are in F4 leading cirrhosis.

Table 5: Show stage of fibrosis in patients.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid F0-F1	581	49.2	49.2	49.2
F2	71	6.0	6.0	55.2
F3	161	13.6	13.6	68.8
F4	368	31.2	31.2	100.0
Total	1181	100.0	100.0	

Fibrosis stage determination using already available variables

The means and standard deviations of age of patients, baseline viral load, fibroscan score, platelet count,

and alkaline phosphatase are 42.523 ± 12.9788 , $1453430.51 \pm 7613073.991$, 13.9569 ± 12.49916 , $198845.2159 \pm 61816.52915$, 296.513 ± 131.1257 respectively (table 6).

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age of Patient	1176	14.0	85.0	42.523	12.9788
Baseline Viral Load	1181	135	107911144	1453430.51	7613073.991
Fibroscan score	1181	2.60	75.00	13.9569	12.49916
Platelet Count	1181	17900.00	281000.00	198845.2159	61816.52915
Alkaline Phosphatase	1181	51.0	1154.0	296.513	131.1257
Valid N (list wise)	1176				

The Independent sample T- test results for stage F0-F1 & F2 for variables i.e. ALT and AST Score is given in the table below showing statistically significant relationship of these variables with fibrosis stages of F0-F1 and F2 determined fibro scan score with $p < 0.05$.

Table 7: T test results of F0-F1 and F2

: T test results of F0-F1 and F2						
	Fibrosis Stage	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P Value
ALT	F0-F1	581	52.382	29.2279	1.2126	.000
	F2	71	74.352	46.2228	5.4856	
AST	F0-F1	581	55.240	37.6598	1.5624	.001
	F2	71	76.958	49.1913	5.8379	

The Independent sample T- test results for stage F3 & F4 for variables i.e. ALT and AST Score is given in the table below showing statistically significant relationship of all these variables with fibrosis stages determined fibro scan score with $p < 0.05$.

Table 8: T test results of F3 & F4

	Fibrosis Stage	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
ALT	F3	161	80.280	35.9945	2.8368	.001
	F4	368	96.747	81.6962	4.2587	
AST	F3	161	74.286	37.6021	2.9635	.000
	F4	368	96.231	75.8220	3.9525	

Univariate analysis: Univariate analysis for ALT and AST score showed a statistically significant relationship with Person's correlation coefficients (R) values. Squared Value = .674 (P value = .000)

DISCUSSION:

Our study showed that, Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) can predict advance stage of fibrosis and cirrhosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C infection. In these patients, a liver biopsy and fibroscan may not be necessary. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) are the enzymes present in hepatic cells which are important for the ongoing metabolism. However, any injury to the liver causes the hepatic cells to release these enzymes in blood in a much greater amount than normal which is indicative of liver disease. According to our study, serum aminotransferase levels i.e. AST and ALT have significant relation with advanced stages of fibrosis. The comparison of sensitivity and specificity of aminotransferase levels with fibroscan for F4 stage showed that AST had sensitivity of 82.6 and specificity of 79.0 while for ALT, the sensitivity was 57.3 and specificity was 50.0.

A liver fibroscan or liver biopsy remains the gold standard for characterizing liver histology, but it is expensive and especially liver biopsy carries some morbidity and, very rarely, mortality risk. Thus, it should be performed in those who would benefit the most from the diagnostic and prognostic perspectives. (4. Julius Wilderl, n.d.)

Similar studies also suggested a significant relation between advanced stages of fibrosis and aminotransferases levels.

CONCLUSION:

AST and ALT can predict advance stage of fibrosis and cirrhosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C infection. In these patients, a liver biopsy and fibro scan may not be necessary.

REFERENCES:

- Smaś M, Skubera M, Wilkosz T, Weryński P, Kołcz J, Olszowska M, Podolec P, Tomkiewicz-Pająk L. Noninvasive assessment of liver status in adult Fontan patients. *Pol Arch Intern Med.* 2019 Feb 19. doi: 10.20452/pamw.4452.
- Afify SM, Tabll A, Nawara HM, El Kassas M, Elfert A, Seno M, El-Kousy S. Five Fibrosis Biomarkers Together with Serum

- Ferritin Level to Diagnose Liver Fibrosis and Cirrhosis. *Clin Lab*. 2018 Oct 1;64(10):1685-1693. doi: 10.7754/Clin.Lab.2018.180502.
3. Fouad SA¹, Esmat S, Omran D, Rashid L, Kobaisi MHWorld J Gastroenterol. Noninvasive assessment of hepatic fibrosis in Egyptian patients with chronic hepatitis C virus infection. 2012 Jun 21;18(23):2988-94. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v18.i23.2988.
 4. Julius Wilder^{1,2} and Keyur Patel^{1,2} The clinical utility of FibroScan[®] as a noninvasive diagnostic test for liver disease *Med Devices (Auckl)*. 2014; 7: 107–114. Published online 2014 May 3. doi: 10.2147/MDER.S46943 *Minerva Med*. 2019 May 6. doi: 10.23736/S0026-4806.19.06109-3. [Epub ahead of print]
 5. Non-invasive assessment of liver fibrosis in HCV patients compared to liver biopsy: the experience of tertiary level Hospital in Serbia. Preveden T1,2, Vereš B1, Ružić M1,2, Pete M1,2, Luzza F3, Pellicano R4, Abenavoli [PubMed]. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2013 Jul;57(2):240-6. doi: 10.1093/cid/cit245. Epub 2013 Apr 16.
 6. Noninvasive serum fibrosis markers for screening and staging chronic hepatitis C virus patients in a large US cohort. Holmberg SD1, Lu M, Rupp LB, Lamerato LE, Moorman AC, Vijayadeva V, Boscarino JA, Henkle EM, Gordon SC; Chronic Hepatitis Cohort Study (CHeCS) Investigators. [PubMed]. *J Formos Med Assoc*. 2015 Oct;114(10):923-8. doi: 10.1016/j.jfma.2015.07.004. Epub 2015 Aug 13.
 7. Fibrosis index based on four factors better predicts advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis than aspartate aminotransferase/platelet ratio index in chronic hepatitis C patients. Wang CC1, Liu CH2, Lin CL3, Wang PC1, Tseng TC1, Lin HH1, Kao JH4 *Turk J Gastroenterol*. 2011 Jun;22(3):279-85.
 8. AST-platelet ratio index, Forns index and FIB-4 in the prediction of significant fibrosis and cirrhosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C. Güzelbulut F1, Çetinkaya ZA, Sezıklı M, Yaşar B, Ozkara S, Övünç AO. *Turk J Gastroenterol*. 2012 Aug;23(4):353-8.
 9. AST-platelet ratio index in the prediction of significant fibrosis and cirrhosis in patients with chronic hepatitis B. Güzelbulut F1, Sezıklı M, Akkan-Çetinkaya Z, Yaşar B, Özkara S, Kurdaş-Övünç AO. *J Clin Lab Anal*. 2019 May 22:e22922. doi: 10.1002/jcla.22922. [Epub ahead of print]
 10. Noninvasive indicators predict advanced liver fibrosis in autoimmune hepatitis patients. Liu L1, Cao J2, Zhong Z1, Guo Z1, Jiang Y1, Bai Y2, Xu J2. *Ann Hepatol*. 2017 November-December;16(6):862-873. doi: 10.5604/01.3001.0010.5276.
 11. Fibrogenic/Angiogenic Linker for Non-Invasive Assessment of Hepatic Fibrosis Staging in Chronic Hepatitis C Among Egyptian Patients. Toson EA1, Shiha GE2, Abdelgaleel AE3. *Arab J Gastroenterol*. 2016 Jun;17(2):78-83. doi: 10.1016/j.ajg.2016.05.002. Epub 2016 Jun 25.
 12. FibroScan, APRI, FIB4, and GUCI: Role in prediction of fibrosis and response to therapy in Egyptian patients with HCV infection. Yosry A1, Fouad R1, Alem SA2, Elsharkawy A1, El-Sayed M1, Asem N3, Hassan E4, Ismail A5, Esmat G1. *Antivir Ther*. 2015;20(2):185-92. doi: 10.3851/IMP2805. Epub 2014 Jun 18.
 13. Non-invasive fibrosis assessment predicts sustained virological response to telaprevir with pegylated interferon and ribavirin for chronic hepatitis C. Ogawa E1, Furusyo N, Shimizu M, Ihara T, Hayashi T, Harada Y, Toyoda K, Murata M, Hayashi J. *Clin Lab*. 2019 Jan 1;65(1). doi: 10.7754/Clin.Lab.2018.180607.
 14. Evaluation of Serum Alpha-Fetoprotein Level in Chronic Hepatitis C Patients. Yang N, Li Z, Yan M, Xiao W, Zhang W, Long Y, Cheng Y, Ming K, Xu B *Vnitř Lek*. 2002 Oct;48(10):924-8.
 15. [Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) more than alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels predict the progression of liver fibrosis in chronic HCV infection]. [Article in Czech] Stránský J1, Ryzlová M, Striteský J, Horák J. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2000 Apr;15(4):386-90.
 16. Aspartate aminotransferase: alanine aminotransferase ratio in chronic hepatitis C infection: is it a useful predictor of cirrhosis? Park GJ1, Lin BP, Ngu MC, Jones DB, Katelaris PH. [PubMed] *Am J Gastroenterol*. 1998 Jan;93(1):44-8.
 17. AST/ALT ratio predicts cirrhosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C virus infection. Sheth SG1, Flamm SL, Gordon FD, Chopra S. [PubMed] *Arch Intern Med*. 2003 Jan 27;163(2):218-24.
 18. Validity and clinical utility of the aspartate aminotransferase-alanine aminotransferase ratio in assessing disease severity and prognosis in patients with hepatitis C virus-related chronic liver disease. Giannini E1, Risso D, Botta F, Chiarbonello B, Fasoli A, Malfatti F, Romagnoli P, Testa E, Ceppa P, Testa R. [PubMed] *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2002 Nov;97(11):2855-60.
 19. The 1-year and 3-month prognostic utility of the AST/ALT ratio and model for end-stage liver disease score in patients with viral liver cirrhosis. Giannini E1, Botta F, Testa E, Romagnoli P,

- Polegato S, Malfatti F, Fumagalli A, Chiarbonello B, Risso D, Testa R. [\[PubMed\]](#) *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2001 Nov;96(11):3142-6.
20. Serum aminotransferase levels and platelet counts as predictors of degree of fibrosis in chronic hepatitis C virus infection. Pohl AI, Behling C, Oliver D, Kilani M, Monson P, Hassanein T. [\[PubMed\]](#)